

Welcome to the Simulation-as-a-Service Hub for Energy Research

Unlock the power of advanced simulations to drive innovation in energy research. Our Simulation-as-a-Service (SaaS) Hub provides an intuitive, scalable, and collaborative environment designed to simplify the use of simulations for researchers, engineers, and decision-makers.

Learn about using
simulation

Look for simulation
software

What co-simulation
framework fits best?

Create a simulation
scenario

Run your simulation

Share your results

Learn how to use Simulation in your research

Software Registry

Name	License	Open Source	Keywords
AMIRIS	Apache License 2.0	Yes	Agent-based Modelling, Market Model
ASSUME	GNU Affero General Public License v3.0	Yes	Market Model, Reinforcement Learning
DaceDSX	MIT, Apache License 2.0	Yes	Distributed Simulation, Co-Simulation, Traffic, Energy
FAME (Open Framework for distributed Agent-based Modelling of Energy systems)	Apache License 2.0	Yes	Agent-based Modelling, Energy Systems
mosaik	GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0	Yes	Co-Simulation, Energy System Simulation
Framework Open Energy Modelling Framework (oemof-solph)	MIT	Yes	Energy System Simulation
PyPSA	MIT	Yes	Power System Analysis
VILLASframework	Apache License 2.0	Yes	Realtime-Co-Simulation, Geographically Distributed

Add new software

What co-simulation framework should I use?

Choosing the appropriate simulation framework is crucial for the success of your research project. Depending on your requirements for scalability, flexibility, and interoperability, each framework offers unique strengths. Our platform currently supports three powerful simulation frameworks: VILLASframework, mosaik, and DaceDS.

VILLASframework is an open source software toolbox that provides infrastructure services to support Geographically Distributed Real Time Simulations of Cyber Physical Systems in the energy domain. With VILLAS, users can couple software- and hardware-based simulators as well as real devices for Hardware-in-the-Loop experiments.

mosaik provides a flexible and modular environment for co-simulation, making it an excellent choice for studying complex energy systems. Its simple API allows seamless integration and orchestration of various models.

DaceDS is a data-centric distributed simulation framework that enables flexible simulator coupling, data integration, and orchestration via Apache Kafka's publish/subscribe paradigm.

Still not sure which framework to choose?

Take a quiz:

Do you want to use Hardware in the Loop?

Yes

No

Do you want to do parallel simulation?

Yes

No

Do you want to use python to create your scenario?

Yes

No

Create a simulation scenario

Pick a Co-simulation Framework to create a scenario

VILLASframework

Run my own simulation or reuse
one

Run a co-simulation

Run an existing scenario

Scenario 1	Reuse
Scenario 2	Reuse
Scenario 3	Reuse
Scenario 4	Reuse
Scenario 5	Reuse

Upload your files

Start

Results

[Download results as zip](#)[Share your results](#)[Share your scenario](#)

Simulators

- pandapower
 - Bus
 - Line
 - Transformer
- GridOperator
 - + GridOperator
- PV
 - + PVPanel


```
graph LR; Bus[Bus] --> GridOperator[Grid Operator]; Line[Line] --> GridOperator; GridOperator --> PVPanel[PVPanel]; Bus --> PVPanel;
```

Share your scenario

Save scenario

Run scenario

- Nodes filtern
- round
 - Netzwerk
 - http in
 - http response
 - http request
 - villas - websocket
 - tcp in
 - tcp out
 - tcp request
 - udp in
 - udp out
 - villas - socket
 - villas - webrtc
 - Sequenz

- Share your scenario
- Save scenario
- Run scenario

General

Scenario

Catalog

Upload Scenario

Export Scenario

Reset Scenario

Run Scenario

Abort Run

Setup SCE Viewer Topology Connectors Scenario Run

General

ScenarioID: 1652363394662

Involved Domains: communication, traffic

Scenario Start: 00:00

Scenario End: 00:08:20

RandomSeed: 23

Synchronized Participants: 2

Building Blocks

MATSimWrapper1

ID: MATSimWrapper1

Type: MATSimWrapper

Domain: traffic

Layer: meso

StepLength: 1000

Resources: RoadMap: Manhattan.matsim.network.xml
Traffic: Manhattan.high.traffic.East.plans.xml
RoadMap: Town01_extended.network.xml
Traffic: Town01.noplans.xml

Responsibilities: 1561603076,1586207576,1586207579,1595548255,1595548256,1598885931,1598885934,1598908736,1598908738,1598908760,1598908776,213175!

Results: modalsplit-output

Synchronized: Participating

Observers: [Add Observer](#)

Share your scenario

Save scenario

Run scenario